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In recent years, extensive research has been conducted worldwide on the rapidly developing Islamic financial system, which is gaining a growing share of the global financial space. Priority research directions include clarifying the functional elements of introducing Islamic banking services into commercial banking activities, improving the legal and regulatory framework for implementing Islamic banking services, forming the sources for introducing these services, conducting econometric analyses of the influencing factors, and enhancing the implementation of Islamic banking services in the national economy.

In the context of ensuring the socio-economic development of the New Uzbekistan, special attention is being paid to establishing Islamic banks, insurance organizations, and investment funds. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasized in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020: "The time has come to create a legal framework for the introduction of Islamic financial services in our country. Experts from the Islamic Development Bank and other international financial institutions will be involved in this process" [2].

In Uzbekistan, 80% of business entities are financed through internal sources, and only a quarter utilize credit services. Furthermore, 85% of bank assets belong to state-owned banks, which offer only a limited number of products for financing small and medium-sized businesses. Consequently, most enterprises do not consider banks as a preferred source of financing. This has led to a lack of attention to financial reporting by business entities and the frequent misrepresentation of their actual financial position in official reports submitted to tax authorities.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Therefore, it is essential to further expand the theoretical foundations of Islamic banking services, finance fixed assets intended for legal entities through Islamic window services based on murabaha contracts, ensure the stable repayment of allocated funds, and conduct research aimed at forecasting the influence of SOFR (Secured Overnight Financing Rate) rates on Islamic financing in commercial banks.

Research by foreign scholars such as Abdul Rahim, Mohammed Obaidullah, Ledgerwood Joanna, Deena Burjorjee, Khan A, Masyita Dian, Susan Johnson, Kiran Siddiqi, Halima Begum, Ferdous Alam, Aslam Mia, Faruk Bhuiyan, Ahmad Bashawir Abdul Ghani, Adnan Zikri, Ben Abdelkader, Dewan Alamgir, Kabir Hassan, Faruk Abdullah, Fersi, Marwa, Boujelbene, Mouna, Zeller M, Rauf S, Mahmood T, and others has studied the use of Islamic microfinance to reduce poverty and support its implementation through non-governmental non-profit organizations [3]. In Uzbekistan, national scholars such as Shaykh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf have addressed issues of Islamic banking in works like "Market and Related Issues" [5] and "Debt and Related Issues" [6]. S. Abrorov conducted a scientific study titled "Prospects for the Introduction of Sukuk—Islamic Securities in Uzbekistan." Similarly, researchers such as H. Nusratkhujaev, Kh. Khasanov, and T. Bobokulov have also contributed to the field of Islamic economics and banking.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses qualitative and quantitative methods, including expert interviews, analysis of legal frameworks, and statistical data from the Central Bank and international financial institutions. The collected data is analyzed through comparative analysis and trend evaluation to assess the feasibility, demand, and regulatory challenges of developing Islamic microfinance services in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Poverty remains one of the great tragedies of the modern era. About 9.2% of the world's population, or 689 million people, live in poverty (earning less than \$1.90 USD per day) [8]. One of the main causes of this is the limited access to financial services. Indeed, the poor not only require credit but also need access to various banking services such as savings, money transfers, and insurance. Since commercial banks are primarily concentrated in metropolitan areas, microfinance institutions have emerged to fill this gap.

Microfinance institutions that operate in accordance with Islamic Shariah principles are known as Islamic microfinance institutions. Islamic microfinance involves offering financial services to clients based on Islamic values such as brotherhood, solidarity, and partnership. In addition, business financing is carried out on a partnership basis between the institution and the client.

The microcredit offered by traditional microfinance institutions often includes *riba* (interest), which is prohibited by Islamic law, thus preventing many Muslim entrepreneurs from using such services. To better understand the demand for Islamic microfinance, it is important to examine the top 20 countries with the largest Muslim populations (Table 1).

Table 1. Top 20 Countries with the largest muslim populations [9].

No	Countries	Population in 2022	Muslim Population	Share of Muslims in National Population (%)	Share of Muslims in World Population (%)
1	Indonesia	279,134,505	229,000,000	87.20%	12.70%
2	Pakistan	229,488,994	200,400,000	96.50%	11.10%
3	India	1,406,631,776	195,000,000	14.20%	10.90%
4	Bangladesh	167,885,689	153,700,000	90.40%	9.20%
5	Nigeria	216,746,934	99,000,000	49.60%	5.30%
6	Egypt	106,156,692	87,500,000	92.35%	4.90%
7	Iran	86,022,837	82,500,000	99.40%	4.60%
8	Turkey	85,561,976	79,850,000	99.20%	4.60%
9	Algeria	45,350,148	41,240,913	99.00%	2.70%
10	Sudan	45,992,020	39,585,777	97.00%	1.90%
11	Iraq	42,164,965	38,465,864	95.70%	1.90%
12	Morocco	37,772,756	37,930,989	99.00%	2.00%
13	Ethiopia	120,812,698	35,600,000	33.90%	1.80%
14	Afghanistan	40,754,388	34,836,014	99.60%	1.80%
15	Saudi Arabia	35,844,909	31,878,000	97.10%	1.60%
16	China	1,448,471,400	28,127,500	1.73%	1.60%
17	Yemen	31,154,867	27,784,498	99.10%	1.50%
18	Uzbekistan	35,382,084	26,550,000	96.50%	1.70%
19	Nigeria	26,083,660	21,101,926	98.30%	1.00%
20	Russia	145,805,947	20,000,000	13.50%	1.00%

From this table, we can see that over 1.5 billion Muslims live in the top 20 countries. Globally, the total Muslim population exceeds 1.9 billion, accounting for 24.7% of the world's population [7]. Unfortunately, 50% of the world's poorest people are Muslims [Sema Yılmaz Genç, "Poverty in Muslim Countries: Policy Recommendations over the Gulf Cooperation Council," International Congress of Islamic Economy, Finance and Ethics, Proceedings Book, 2019, Istanbul | Turkey]. This means that 1 in every 5 Muslims lives in extreme poverty. Hence, it is evident that the demand for Islamic microfinance is very high.

Muslim countries possess around 70% of the world's natural resources, including oil, natural gas, gold, copper, and others. Moreover, many Muslim-majority countries have strong agricultural sectors. Despite this, several factors contribute to the high poverty rate among Muslims, including widespread corruption, deeply rooted bureaucracy, rampant misappropriation of state property, the lack of a systematic zakat collection and distribution mechanism, and the fact that Islamic microfinance still accounts for only 1% of total Islamic finance capital (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of Islamic Microfinance [7].

Islamic microfinance institutions are divided into two groups: commercial and non-commercial forms.

- The commercial form includes microcredit and micro-equity (entrepreneurship based on partnership).

- The non-commercial form includes waqf (endowment) funds.

All types of microfinance institutions must strictly adhere to the following three core principles:

Riba (interest) – Any form of interest is strictly prohibited. Simply put, this means increasing wealth by lending money without any productive effort. Any form of credit with interest is an example of this.

Gharar (uncertainty or ambiguity) – This refers to uncertainty, vagueness, or a lack of sufficient information. In such transactions, both the seller and the buyer must have equal knowledge about the product. The main goal of prohibiting gharar in Islamic law is to prevent one party from having an unfair advantage over the other. Gharar does not create anything extra but instead generates income at the expense of someone else losing or suffering damage. Examples include: selling a car that has been damaged but claiming it is undamaged, selling a sack of potatoes by covering the lower part with better-quality ones while claiming it is of uniform quality, or selling goods to a buyer who is unaware of the market price at a much higher price.

Maysir (speculation or gambling) – This refers to unsubstantiated entrepreneurship where profit or loss is made without any effort, which is akin to gambling. An example of maysir is gambling, where wealth is acquired without labor, at the expense of someone else's loss (Table 2) [7].

Table 2. Difference Between Traditional Microfinance and Islamic Microfinance [4].

Service Types	Traditional Microfinance	Islamic Microfinance
Liabilities	Shareholders' equity, deposit funds	Shareholders' equity, deposit funds, zakat and waqf funds
Assets	Fixed assets, interest-bearing loans	Fixed assets, Islamic financial instruments
Financing Method	Money (Cash or non-cash)	Assets or goods
Target Groups	Women	Families
Employee Incentives	In cash	In cash and religious incentives
In Case of Loan Default	Pressure on group members	Pressure on family members
Social Development Program	Secular, behavioral, ethical, and social development	Includes religious behavior

If we analyze this table, we can see that Islamic microfinance differs from traditional microfinance in terms of liabilities formation, assets, financing methods, target groups, and other aspects. It is important to note that this table compares the activities of Islamic and traditional microfinance organizations in countries where both operate side by side.

The main objective of microfinance is to assist the poor by creating conditions for them to work and earn income. In modern terms, there is a saying, "Don't give the poor a fish, teach them how to fish." This is a common principle for both Islamic and traditional microfinance.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The development of Islamic microfinance services in Uzbekistan holds great potential for fostering inclusive economic growth, reducing poverty, and promoting social justice. As the country continues its reforms toward a more diversified and sustainable financial system, integrating Islamic finance—particularly microfinance—into the national financial landscape can address the unmet needs of specific segments of the population, especially those in rural areas or with limited access to conventional banking.

Despite initial steps being taken in this direction, such as public discussions and pilot projects, the sector still faces several challenges. These include the lack of a comprehensive legal and regulatory framework tailored to Islamic finance, insufficient awareness among the general population and financial practitioners, and a shortage of professionals trained in Islamic finance principles. Additionally, the absence of dedicated Islamic microfinance institutions and supporting infrastructure hinders rapid development.

International experience shows that Islamic microfinance institutions, when well-regulated and integrated into the broader financial ecosystem, can play a vital role in supporting small businesses, women entrepreneurs, and low-income households. By operating on principles such as profit-and-loss sharing (*mudarabah* and *musharakah*), interest-free loans (*qard al-hasan*), and asset-backed financing (*ijarah* and *murabaha*), these institutions can ensure ethical, inclusive, and Shariah-compliant financial services.

For Uzbekistan to fully harness the benefits of Islamic microfinance, it is crucial to adopt a strategic approach. This includes developing a clear legal and regulatory framework, building public-private partnerships, encouraging academic research and training, and raising public awareness. Government support, collaboration with international Islamic financial institutions, and the use of digital technologies can significantly accelerate progress in this sector. Ultimately, the successful implementation of Islamic microfinance services in Uzbekistan can contribute to broader socio-economic development and support the country's vision for a more inclusive and just financial system.

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